

Centralisation Without Measurement Reform: A Response to “Building NHS Resilience to Ransomware” White Paper

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Working Paper – Not Peer Reviewed¹. This response engages with the white paper 'Building NHS Resilience to Ransomware' by Kello and colleagues, which diagnoses NHS cybersecurity failure as inconsistent implementation rather than a lack of knowledge, and proposes a Cyber Leadership Framework backed by centralised enforcement. It accepts that diagnosis and extends it: centralising the enforcement of static compliance metrics will replicate the problem it sets out to solve, because static metrics cannot track a threat environment that does not stand still. A cross-sectional analysis of 171 NHS Trusts supports the concern, finding no statistically significant association between resource scale and compliance outcomes – a null result consistent with the prediction that the metric captures positional attainment rather than capability. The response proposes a velocity-based complement, the Cyber Progress Measure, which rewards directional improvement over fixed targets and would let the white paper's centralisation architecture do the work it sets out to do.

¹ v2 (June 2026): Reference to Shabad (2026a) updated to align with the published version of that analysis: quartile-level compliance figures withdrawn; overall null finding ($p = 0.88$; Cohen's $d = 0.02$) retained.
v1 (April 2026): Original submission.

1 Introduction

Kello et al. (2026) address a question that has persisted through every major NHS cyber incident since WannaCry: why does a health system that possesses credible cybersecurity frameworks continue to suffer ransomware attacks that disrupt patient care? Their answer – that the problem is one of inconsistent implementation rather than absent knowledge – is well supported by the qualitative evidence they present. The proposed Cyber Leadership Framework offers a structured set of governance interventions targeting board literacy, consistent measurement, supply chain oversight, centralised shared services, cultural change, and funding reform. Each pillar addresses a real and documented weakness.

This response does not challenge that diagnosis. It extends it, drawing on quantitative analysis of 171 NHS Trusts and a programme of research into how governance architectures systematically reproduce the conditions for failure – even in organisations that are formally compliant, well-resourced, and operating in good faith.

2 The Measurement Paradox

The white paper is at its most perceptive on the question of compliance. Observation 5 states plainly that “compliance and good operational risk management are not the same thing.” The paper documents cases where Trusts declared DSPT compliance yet were subsequently found, after a ransomware attack, to have provided “a generous – even misleading – self-appraisal”. This is an important finding, and the white paper is right to foreground it.

Yet the paper’s prescriptions reinstate the paradigm it critiques. Pillar 3 proposes “a mandatory minimum set of cyber risk metrics that are applied consistently across all NHS Trusts, enabling comparability and system-wide oversight”. The incentivisation section recommends adding cybersecurity maturity as a field in NHS Trust rankings. The accountability section calls for an annual attestation approved and signed by the Board Chair. Each of these is a static measurement instrument: it captures positional attainment at a point in time. The paper diagnoses the problem correctly; the prescriptions, however, reinstate the same measurement architecture that the diagnosis calls into question.

The structural reason why static metrics cannot resolve this problem lies in Van Valen's (1973) Red Queen Effect. Adversaries evolve continuously; a static defensive posture, therefore, amounts to regression, not stasis. As a Trust's digital estate grows, the complexity of securing it grows non-linearly – large organisations must run faster merely to stand still. DSPT compliance, assessed at a fixed reporting date, cannot distinguish between a Trust that has maintained unchanged 2020-era controls and one that has continuously retired security debt. Both receive identical ratings. The NCSC's 2025 Annual Review makes the external pressure explicit: a 50% year-on-year increase in highly significant incidents, an increase for the third consecutive year (National Cyber Security Centre, 2025).

This mechanism has a testable empirical implication: if complexity grows non-linearly with organisational scale, better-resourced Trusts should not outperform smaller ones on static compliance – they face a proportionally harder maintenance problem. A cross-sectional analysis of 171 NHS Trusts, pairing 2023/24 financial returns with 2024/25 DSPT compliance outcomes, is consistent with this prediction (Shabad, 2026a). Mean total staff costs showed no statistically significant difference between compliant organisations (£427.0m) and non-compliant organisations (£420.5m) – Welch's t-test yielded $p = 0.88$ with Cohen's $d = 0.02$. The null is consistent with the predicted consequence of a static framework applied to a non-static threat environment; alternative explanations – including differential rates of self-assessment accuracy across Trust sizes – cannot be excluded from a cross-sectional analysis alone.

Centralising enforcement of this measurement architecture would therefore not resolve the underlying problem – it would replicate it uniformly. Consistent DSPT ratings across all Trusts do not constitute consistent evidence of cyber resilience; they constitute consistent evidence of positional attainment at a fixed date. The risk is not that the NHS would lack oversight, but that it would have uniformly distributed assurance of the wrong property.

A velocity-based alternative – measuring the rate of vulnerability closure, security debt retirement, and adaptive response – would complement the white paper's centralisation architecture by ensuring that what is measured nationally corresponds to what actually predicts defensive capability. Research on ecological rationality (Gigerenzer and Gaissmaier, 2011) demonstrates that in uncertain environments, simple velocity heuristics outperform complex state-based rules. The Cyber Progress Measure (Shabad, 2026a) applies this principle to cybersecurity governance: it rewards directional improvement under constraint

rather than static positional attainment, and it remains robust across the heterogeneous Trust sizes and resource profiles the DSPT analysis documents.

The administrative burden imposed by static compliance reinforces this problem. The current DSPT v7, while reformed from its predecessor's 100+ prescriptive controls to 47 CAF-aligned contributing outcomes, retains the same state-based architecture: organisations are assessed against a fixed profile at a fixed reporting date. For large Trusts managing complex digital estates, the administrative cost of annual re-evidencing is substantial – and the return on that investment, as the n = 171 analysis documents, is a metric that fails to distinguish between organisations that are genuinely improving and those that are standing still (Shabad, 2026a).

A velocity-based alternative, such as the Cyber Progress Measure, reduces this burden precisely because it measures fewer things more accurately. Three components – vulnerability closure rate, security debt retirement, and adaptive response capacity – replace a comprehensive but static checklist with a focused measure of directional momentum. For Trusts, this means less administrative overhead and a metric that rewards the operational work they are already doing. For DHSC and NHS England, it means a national dashboard that distinguishes genuine improvement from compliant stasis.

3 Signal Suppression and the Limits of Board Accountability

The white paper's Pillar 2 recommends experiential scenario-based exercises, board education designed for “decision competence rather than just awareness”, and conducting board discussions in operational language. These are sensible interventions. The paper also identifies the correct anti-pattern: “a culture in which senior leaders signal pride in limited technology understanding”.

What the paper does not examine is how risk information reaches the board in the first place. Hall's (1976) distinction between high-context and low-context communication cultures provides the analytical frame. In NHS governance – and in British professional culture more broadly – operational urgency is systematically softened as it moves upward through reporting hierarchies. This is not a communication failure; it is a structural feature of

institutional communication norms shaped by what Hood (2011) terms the “blame game” in risk regulation regimes. Phrases such as “concerns have been identified”, “issues are being monitored”, or “there may be an increased risk” are not accidents. They are the safest way to surface uncertainty in a governance environment that punishes false alarms more visibly than unresolved exposure (Shabad, 2025).

Research into this mechanism – termed *cue validity collapse* – integrates Hall’s communication theory with Kahneman’s (2011) dual-process cognition and Simon’s (1956) bounded rationality to explain how high-context communication norms systematically degrade the reliability of urgency signals (Shabad, 2026c). British professional culture encodes warning severity through implicit cues: hedged language, passive voice, and diplomatic softening. Overloaded executives apply a cognitively rational heuristic: “if it were truly urgent, the warning would be explicit”. The environment-heuristic mismatch produces systematic false negatives. Critical threats are classified as routine concerns because the communication register that professional norms demand is identical to the register used for genuinely routine matters. Vaughan’s (1996) analysis of the Challenger disaster documented the same dynamic: engineers communicated risk in the professional register their culture demanded, and managers interpreted the absence of explicit alarm as implicit endorsement.

Three NHS and public sector cases demonstrate that this pattern is a structural consequence of how British institutions process risk warnings, not a feature of any single sector. The three successive CareCERT cyber alerts distributed before WannaCry did not generate a board-level response in the majority of affected Trusts – a finding documented in the National Audit Office investigation (National Audit Office, 2018) and the subsequent lessons-learned review (NHS England, 2018). The Post Office Horizon Inquiry’s Final Report documents how technical concerns about the Horizon system were consistently reformulated into reassurances as they moved through the Post Office’s governance chain, rendering board-level oversight structurally ineffective (Post Office Horizon IT Inquiry, 2025). Grenfell Tower presents a third instance of the same institutional dynamic across a different sector (Grenfell Tower Inquiry, 2024). Each case reflects a structural consequence of how British governance processes risk information at the board interface.

The white paper’s proposed board questions – e.g., “What assurance do we have that accountability is meaningful rather than nominal?” – will receive answers delivered in precisely this softened register. The deeper problem is that the question has no operational

anchor: a board member cannot distinguish a meaningful answer from a nominal one without an explicit criterion for what meaningful accountability looks like in practice. Board members applying fast cognitive filters under time pressure will categorise these responses as routine unless the communication architecture itself is redesigned.

This is not an argument against board literacy. It is an argument that board literacy alone is insufficient without parallel redesign of the communication channel. Explicit severity classification, active voice imperatives, and binary escalation triggers – architectural interventions that address the signal before it reaches the receiver – would complement the white paper’s receiver-side interventions.

4 Centralisation and the Coordination-Cost Ceiling

The white paper’s strongest analytical contribution is its recognition that centralisation is the only viable path to consistent cybersecurity across a fragmented landscape of over 200 autonomous Trusts. Observation 7 is incisive: “Local IT managers will almost always insist upon the unique specialness of their requirements... They rarely welcome off-the-shelf central offerings and will point to increased concentration risk. But they are almost always wrong in terms of achieving optimum systemic cybersecurity and value for money”. This is the correct structural diagnosis, and it is a position that requires intellectual courage to state as directly as the authors do. What the diagnosis does not address is the implementation paradox it creates: the same local specialists who resist centralisation are the only people qualified to execute it. In a sector where skilled cybersecurity personnel are structurally scarce, coercing their cooperation is not an available option – their alienation would directly create the capacity bottleneck centralisation is designed to resolve. The question is therefore not whether to override local resistance, but how to make centralisation worth accepting on its own terms.

The scarcity of qualified personnel is not a local observation – it is a structural feature of the CNI sector as a whole, and healthcare is unambiguously within that sector: designated CNI under the NIS Regulations 2018 and in scope of the forthcoming Cyber Security and Resilience Bill. The DSIT study on cyber security in the UK critical infrastructure provides direct evidence: when asked what they would do with an unlimited budget, practitioners across sectors converged on an identical constraint. As one water sector manager put it:

“There are just not enough of us to go around, so even if we had all the money in the world, we couldn’t recruit the people we needed” (Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, 2025, p. 27). When skilled personnel are structurally unavailable regardless of budget, the optimisation problem changes. The question is not whether to centralise but how fast centralisation can proceed given fixed capacity, and what happens at the coordination bottleneck when hundreds of Trusts simultaneously depend on central capability.

Brooks (1995) demonstrated in software project management that beyond a certain threshold, adding more people and more parallel work makes complex systems slower, not faster. Little’s Law Little (1961) formalises this: work-in-progress beyond capacity causes non-linear lead time expansion. The Theory of Constraints formalises the complementary point: sustainable throughput improvement requires identifying and protecting the system’s binding constraint rather than attempting to optimise all components simultaneously (Goldratt, 1990). Centralising cybersecurity services across the NHS estate may reduce inconsistency at the Trust level, but simultaneously creates a single coordination bottleneck where the same non-linear cost dynamics apply. The white paper’s own citation of the NPfIT failure – “a near unmitigated disaster [that] has left deep scars” – provides historical evidence that centralisation without coordination-cost management produces the same failure pattern at a higher organisational level.

Work-in-progress limits, velocity-based metrics, and staged sequencing of centralisation would address this risk. These mechanisms ensure that the centralisation the white paper advocates proceeds at the pace organisational capacity can sustain rather than at the pace political urgency demands – a distinction with direct operational consequences for the shared services architecture the paper proposes.

5 Adoption Architecture and the Case for Centralised Threat Intelligence

The white paper’s recommendations implicitly assume that Trusts and central bodies will adopt proposed governance reforms because they are structurally sound. This assumption overlooks a well-established principle in behavioural economics: the quality of a governance instrument is a necessary but insufficient condition for its adoption. What determines uptake is the choice architecture – the motivational conditions under which decision-makers

encounter the instrument (Thaler and Sunstein, 2008). Governance reform that redesigns processes without reshaping the motivational layer will encounter predictable adoption resistance.

The white paper applies this logic selectively. Its board education pillar, scenario exercises, and board questions are all receiver-side interventions – they attempt to reshape how boards process and respond to governance demands. But the paper’s approach to local IT specialists is different: where boards are to be educated, local specialists are to be overridden. The paper’s sole prescription for local resistance is accountability transfer – “if Trusts wilfully resist offers of support and capabilities from the centre, then they should be clearly told that this choice shifts the accountability even further in their direction”. This is a coercive rather than motivational response to the same adoption problem. The paper is right that strong central capability is necessary; it does not follow that local expertise is thereby dispensable. The author’s experience managing OT security across geographically distributed CNI operations suggests that central teams depend on local specialists precisely for the contextual knowledge – system dependencies, operational constraints, legacy integration points – that no central function can replicate at scale. A coercive choice architecture risks alienating the local practitioners on whose cooperation effective central oversight depends. The motivational analysis points in a different direction: centralisation needs to be designed as a lever that amplifies local capability rather than a mandate that displaces it.

However, velocity-based governance introduces a dependency that static compliance does not have. A static framework defines the target state independently of the external environment: either the controls are in place, or they are not. A velocity-based framework, by contrast, requires a directional signal – organisations need to know not merely that they must improve, but in which direction the threat landscape is evolving, and therefore where improvement effort should be concentrated. Without this signal, velocity becomes undirected motion rather than an adaptive response.

This is where the white paper’s centralisation argument finds its strongest justification – not in enforcing uniform compliance, but in providing the threat intelligence feed that makes distributed adaptive improvement possible. NHS England already operates this capability precisely: the CSOC processes over 33 billion security signals daily from across the NHS estate, enriched by commercial intelligence from CrowdStrike, Microsoft Defender Threat Intelligence, and Health-ISAC (NHS England, 2025a). Critically, the intelligence product is

healthcare-specific rather than a generic national threat feed: the CSOC Threat Operations team develops custom detections calibrated to NHS environments, curates a prioritised IOC feed scoped explicitly to threats targeting health and social care, and distributes both tactical alerts and strategic assessments through the Threat Intelligence Sharing Platform (TISP) in real time (NHS England, 2025b). NHS Cyber Alerts – such as the three successive advisories issued before WannaCry – are a direct output of this function. Outputs of this kind tell individual Trusts not merely that they must improve, but precisely where to direct their improvement velocity, given the threats actually targeting NHS infrastructure. The central function does not replace local defensive capability; it focuses it. Each Trust retains responsibility for closing vulnerabilities and retiring security debt, but the CSOC/TISP feed ensures that local effort is focused on the attack vectors currently materialising, not on last year’s compliance checklist.

This reframes the centralisation question in terms of the white paper’s own logic. The paper argues that “local IT managers will almost always insist upon the unique specialness of their requirements” and that centralisation of capability is the answer. The motivational analysis suggests a more precise formulation: what should be centralised is the intelligence function that no individual Trust can replicate at sufficient scale, while what should remain distributed is the adaptive response that only local teams – who understand their own digital estates – can execute. Centralised intelligence, distributed execution, velocity-based measurement: these three elements form a governance architecture that is both structurally sound and motivationally aligned with the incentives facing Trusts and the centre alike.

6 The Transparency Paradox in Open Benchmarking

The paper recommends making cybersecurity maturity publicly visible in NHS Trust rankings and enabling national comparability of risk metrics. These proposals serve a legitimate accountability function. However, they rest on an implicit premise – that the audiences for governance transparency are boards seeking improvement, regulators seeking assurance, and the public seeking trust. Cybersecurity governance transparency differs from financial or clinical transparency in one critical respect: detailed disclosure of defensive posture simultaneously serves adversarial audiences. Published league tables of cybersecurity maturity would provide ransomware operators – who, as the white paper itself notes, seek “easy wins” and “gravitate towards the weakest link” – with a publicly available target-

prioritisation tool identifying the least-defended organisations by name. Analysis of FOI responses across NHS Trusts and other public sector bodies reveals that this tension is already producing chaotic, inconsistent results in the absence of central guidance: large trusts routinely refuse disclosure on national security grounds while smaller organisations provide the same information without hesitation, creating a patchwork that serves neither accountability nor security (Shabad, 2026b).

The point is not that transparency is wrong, but that transparency mechanisms in cybersecurity must be designed with adversarial use in mind. Aggregated, anonymised benchmarking that enables boards to compare their own position against national distributions – without publishing individual Trust identities and maturity scores – would preserve the accountability function while limiting the adversarial intelligence value.

7 Toward a Collaborative Research Agenda

The white paper and this response operate on complementary evidence bases. The KCL team brings qualitative depth – practitioner interviews, incident case studies, and a grounded understanding of the operational realities facing NHS CIOs and CISOs. The author’s research programme contributes quantitative analysis (n = 171 Trusts), formal mechanism identification (cue validity collapse, coordination-cost ceilings), and velocity-based governance alternatives.

Several questions that neither body of work answers alone would benefit from integration:

- **Measurement reform:** What would a nationally consistent measurement architecture look like if it assessed adaptive velocity rather than static attainment? The white paper’s call for consistent measurement and this programme’s evidence on velocity-based alternatives are complementary inputs to this design problem.
- **Communication architecture redesign:** How would the white paper’s board accountability interventions interact with explicit severity classification protocols designed to counteract cue validity collapse? Experimental or simulation-based research could test this.
- **Sequencing centralisation:** What work-in-progress constraints should govern the rollout of centralised shared services to prevent the coordination-cost dynamics that defeated NPfIT? The white paper’s operational knowledge of the NHS landscape and

this programme's formal capacity models address different aspects of the same question.

- **Centralised threat intelligence as an enabler of distributed improvement:** What governance architecture would link a national TI/SOC capability to velocity-based measurement at Trust level, so that centralised intelligence informs – rather than replaces – local adaptive response? Pilot studies pairing central threat feeds with CPM tracking at participating Trusts could test this model empirically.
- **Adversary-aware transparency:** How can open benchmarking be designed to serve accountability without serving adversarial intelligence? This requires input from both governance design and threat modelling perspectives.

The white paper identifies the right structural problem – inconsistent implementation across a fragmented landscape – and proposes a governance architecture to address it. The mechanisms identified in this response suggest that the architecture would benefit from four specific reinforcements: replacing static measurement with velocity-based alternatives, redesigning communication channels alongside board competence, sequencing centralisation at the pace capacity permits, and grounding the case for centralisation in the threat intelligence function that makes distributed adaptive improvement possible. These are extensions of the white paper's own logic, not departures from it.

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